

ON THE HISTORICAL EXPLANATION OF THE CONQUEST OF THE ANCIENT USTRUSHANA BY THE ARABS

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Annotation: The first Arab campaigns to Central Asia began with the capture of Marv in 651 under the leadership of Ubaidullah ibn Ziyad. A lot of Arab expeditions to Mowarraunnahr which were in the second half of the 7th century, were organized for the purpose of plundering and exploring the region. The ultima conquest of Movaraunnahr by the Arabs began with the arrival of Qutayba ibn Muslim to the viceroyalty of Khurasan at the beginning of the 8th century. Ustrushana was not left out of such political processes and its subsequent political life consisted of struggles against the Arab caliphate's invasion campaigns, and the history of diplomatic relations like other regions of Central Asia.

Keywords: Ustrushana, Arabs, muslim, Marv, history, territory.

The first appearance of Arabs in Ustrushana coincides with the period of Salm ibn Ziyad (680-683), the third raid of the caliphate on Movaraunnahr during the reign of the viceroy of Khurasan. Arriving in Samarkand Salm ibn Ziyad ordered his assistants to mobilize the army towards Khojand and this army reached Khojand through the territory of Ustrushana and was severely defeated by the local population on the outskirts of the city. The second military campaign of the Arabs to Ustrushana was organized under the command of Muhallab ibn Sufra (697-701)¹.

According to N. Negmatov, Qutayba made the next battle of the Arabs to Ustrushana in 713, when he organized a warfare to Ferghana. Qutayba attacked Choch and Fergana several times in 713-714 and won every time . Those times he

¹ Пардаев М.Х., Гофуров Ж.И. Уструшонанинг илк ўрта аср кишлок маконлари. Тошкент, 2016. Б.296.

attacked not only the settlements of the people located in the plain areas of Ustrushona, but also the towns and villages in the mountainous and mountainous regions. Particularly, Qutayba fought with people wearing black clothes in the Mink fortress according to Ibn Hawqal and al-Istahri's confession and besieged al-Afshin². Most experts suspect that the medieval authors made a mistake by confusing al-Afshinin, who was besieged by Qutayba in Mink, with Heydar al-Afshin who was the prince of Ustrushana, who served in the 20s and 30s of the 9th century during the reign of Caliph Mutasim. In fact, the authors did not make a mistake, but Afshin, who besieged Mink, was the ancestor of another ruler of Ustrushana, whose name was Haydar al-Afshin and has not reached to us. There are those who do not believe in the matter of the "black-clothed" who resisted the Arabs as well. At this point, it should be noted that in ancient and medieval battles, a large number of troops who entered the battle wore the same color clothes to distinguish their comrades from the enemy, and this situation also happened in Ustrushona (Mink Castle) either.

Sogd-Ustrushana relations on some issues of the science which studies Ustrushona belong to this period of the early Middle Ages. In this point, it can be explained according to the genealogy of the governor of Sughd, Gurak, he belonged to the Afshin dynasty of the rulers of Ustrushona, and the uprising of Sughd in 721-722 was connected with the history of Ustrushana³.

Ustrushona was a geographical gate opening in the north-eastern direction to the Fergana Valley, the south side was the right bank of the upper reaches of the Zarafshan river, the north side was the Syr Darya, and the west side was surrounded by Mirzachol in the ancient and early medieval times. Even in the Middle Ages this country had a relatively unique position in various political and economic situations due to its geographical location. For example, it acted as a buffer between Sughd and Choch during the Arab invasion. It was considered important to be aware of the

² Сверчков Л.М. Поселение Мык - источник истории средневековой Уструшаны: Автореф.дисс. ...канд.ист.наук.- Самарканд, 1991. С. 60.

³ Пардаев М.Х., Гофуров Ж.И. Уструшонанинг илк ўрта аср қишлоқ маконлари. Тошкент,2016. Б.297.

situation in Ustrushona for the military-political situation of Choch. The ambassador Fatufarn sent to Choch by Panchikant (Panjikent) khvabusi (ruler, 708-722 AD) Devashtich had to pass through Ustrushona on his way back to Panjikent. But during the days he was in Choch, Ustrushona fell into the rulership of the Arabs and as a result his path was blocked, so fearing to continue his journey alone he returned to Choch. The letter he wrote to his master Devashtich when he was in Choch has come down to us as part of the archive of documents of Mugh Mountain Sugd and is numbered A-14. In lines 16-17 of this letter, Fatufarn writes, "Ustrushanikutakt pgramshtak" - the lands of Ustrushona were occupied⁴. It seems this situation led to an increase in danger not only for the Ustrushans, but also for Panch and Choch.

M. Ishakov says that it is a letter without typical introduction and conclusion that determines to whom the letter or from whom. It seems that this was deliberately hidden due to the complicated situation during the days of the Arab occupation. As for the content of the letter, the unknown author writes as follows: "... (there are) reports that the events in Khojand have calmed down. The people of (Khojand) converted to the religion (or "under the protection") of the emir. There are 14,000 nobles, merchants, officials, working people. They apostatized from their (original) religion. We sent a message about these events. But we heard that (the batman) returned to Huttal(?)⁵.

A number of place names mentioned in the document (Shakat, Btuttam, Pargar, Huttal, etc.) are areas between Khojand and Panjikent (Panchikant). Since the military and political situation in this region was important for Panch, in 720 and 721, the ruler Devashtich sent his spy and used to get information.

According to Tabari, the people of Ustrushan and Panjikent together sought refuge from Alutar, the ruler of Ferghana. However, it is known that this plan did

⁴ Исҳоқов М.И. Илк ўрта асрларда Суғд, Уструшона ва Чоч муносабатларига доир. // "Уструшона Буюк ипак йўлида, унинг минтақалараро сиёсий – иқтисодий ва маданий муносабатларни ривожлантиришдаги ўрни (антик ва ўрта асрлар даврида)" мавзусида ўтказилган республика илмий-амалий анжумани материаллари. Гулистон, 2016. Б.5-7.

⁵ Исҳоқов М.И. илк ўрта асрларда Уструшонанинг сиёсий мақомига доир. // "Қадимий Жиззах воҳаси – Марказий Осиё цивилизацияси тизимида (сиёсий, иқтисодий, маданий ҳаёт)" Республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. Жиззах 2019. Б. 29-31.

not materialize due to Aluttar did not fulfill his promise. Learning about the situation The Arabs killed the incomers on the road near Khojand. After that, the people of Panch also changed their mind about their intention to travel. If these events took place on the eve of 720 AD, Chinese sources, in particular, the Annals of the Tang Dynasty - Tan-shu provide a number of information about Ustrushana.

The viceroy of Khurasan, Asad ibn Abdullah al-Qushayri (735-738), gathered an army to conquer the Khuttalan province in 737. The Khuttalon region which took control of the Wakhsh oasis and its surrounding areas, had maintained its independence until that time, successfully repelled several Arab attacks, and even inflicted a heavy defeat on them. Badr Tarkhan, the governor of Khuttalan at that time, came to the aid of Turk Khan and Hara Bugro with a large army. The allies won in this battle near the Amudarya.

According to Tabari's report, the fighters of the Khagan army, who were happy about this victory and lost their vigilance, dispersed to the villages to celebrate the victory. Assad took advantage of this situation, quickly withdraw his army and hit the allies who are trying to retreat. The Turkic khan returns to his country through Ustrushana, where he is welcomed by Afshin Hara Bugro with great honor and hospitality. In connection with the visit of the khakan and his army, a hurricane blew, purebred vultures and various gifts were presented to the khakan and his army and were hospitable⁶.

Thus, the reasons why the Arabs conquered the Movaraunnahr territories in a short period of time were as follows: The political disunity prevailing in the country and the mutual struggles of the local rulers were very convenient for the Arabs. Qutayba managed to win over the local governors who were in the movement of mutual unification and working for the alliance with various tricks. The Arabs helped one of the warring governors to defeat the other, and then conquered both of them in turn.

⁶ Пардаев М.Х., Гофуров Ж.И. Уструшонанинг илк ўрта аср кишлок маконлари... Б.302.

The Afshins of Ustrushana, a nominal component of the caliphate, were annexed to the state of the Tahirites and became a subordinate country from 822. From this period Ustrushana began to occupy a worthy place among the works of all Arabic-speaking historians and geographers ⁷. It becomes one of the provinces of strategic importance in the political and economic life of the Tahirid state, which united Khurasan and Movaraunnahr. From this period, Ustrushana began to regularly pay 50,000 dirhams (of which 48,000 Muhammadi, 2,000 Musayabi) dirhams to the tahiris as hiraj. The Afshini dynasty, which ruled Ustrushana during the Somani state, was terminated in 893. In later written sources the term Ustrushana began to be used as a geographical name of a specific province, not a political structure. Therefore, Ustrushana will receive the status of a region within the Samanid and subsequent states.

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⁷ Пардаев М.Х., Гофуров Ж.И. Уструшонанинг илк ўрта аср қишлоқ маконлари... Б. 311